

ANALYSIS PROPOSAL

INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS AND ANTI-SYSTEMIC MOVEMENTS: THE NEW APPROACH TO UNDERSTANDING THE WORLD

Prof. Dr. Charles Pennaforte

THE GEOPOLITICAL CONTEXT

- 1991-2008: US geo-economic primacy
- 2008 to the present: US geo-economic decline Gaps for challenging the so-called Liberal Hegemony
- China: Washington's main geopolitical and economic competitor

OUR PROPOSED ANALYSIS: GEOPOLITICAL APPROACH

- **Contestation of Liberal Hegemony (USA)**
- **Theoretical perspective: International relations and the role of challenging global and/or regional powers.**
- **China, Russia, Iran and North Korea: effective action against Washington's project.**
- **The Global South challenges liberal hegemony through diplomatic action.**

ANTI-SYSTEMIC PERSPECTIVE IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PRO-ACTIVE COUNTRIES

ACTIVE COUNTRIES

“PRO-ACTIVE COUNTRIES”

- Confronting the Systemic Core.
- Geopolitical and/or economic pressure from the US and its allies
- Establishment of mutual alliances and/or “strategic” partnerships because of systemic pressure.
- Multipolar world

“ACTIVE COUNTRIES”

- Acting against the systemic core in the “diplomatic” sphere, without direct confrontation.
- Defense of international institutions and multilateralism.
- Multipolar world

CONCEPT OF THE ANTI-SYSTEMIC IMPERATIVE

Definition:

- What does “anti-systemic imperative” mean?

Event

- The Ukrainian War as a catalyst: an event that causes a major change in world dynamics in the medium and long term, by a country of major geopolitical importance or a group of countries. E.g. acceleration of the de-dollarization process.

CHARLES PENNAFORTE

PhD in Internacional Relations from the Nacional University of La Plata (Argentina). Professor of Geopolitics at the Federal University of Pelotas (UFPEL), Brazil.

Coordinator the Laboratory of Geopolitics, International Relations and Antisystemic Movements (LabGRIMA/UFPEL). Founder (2004) and President of the Centre for Studies on Geopolitics and Foreign Affairs (CENEGRI), Brazilian Think Thank.

His books (English) can be found for free on Google search or on the LabGRIMA website and on this platform.

THANK YOU

charles.pennaforde@ufpel.edu.br

<https://wp.ufpel.edu.br/labgrima>

<https://charlespennaforde.pro.br>

<https://cenegri.org.br>

The World System in transition: a panoramic view

EDITED BY
CHARLES PENNAFORTE

CHARLES PENNAFORTE

Antisystemic Movements and International Relations

A theoretical perspective for the
understanding of the World-System

With Foreword by Amine All-Chaafai

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